

3-DOF GAS BEARING SIMULATOR FOR SMALL SATELLITE TESTS WITH AUTOMATED MASS DISPLACEMENT CONTROL TO ELIMINATE DISTURBANCE TORQUES

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ABSTRACT

The focus of testing the Attitude and Orbit Control Subsystem (AOCS) of miniature satellites is set on evaluating the effect of torque exchange devices, as for instance reaction wheels and magnetometers. For simulating a space environment it is therefore one particular task to suspend the satellite freely and frictionless in translational or rotational motion, and allow force-free rotation of a satellite or single components. One appliance that can achieve this even under normal gravitational conditions are gas bearings. However for spherical bearings when the Center of Gravity and Center of Rotation are not equivalent in a system with 3 rotational degrees of freedom, a disturbance torque is induced. Ideally the unit under test of such a three axis air bearing is balanced in such a way that it is indifferent, so that the simulated environment is free of outer forces. A novel method for a gas bearing simulator with three degrees of freedom in rotation without external forces to automatically match the Center of Gravity and Center of Rotation in three dimensions is introduced. A gas bearing simulator is designed to automatically compensate mass displacement using linear actuators for payloads of up to 100 kg. To reach qualification levels the disturbance torque shall be lower than 5×10^{-5} Nm.

Key words: Air-bearing; AOCS simulator; balancing.

INTRODUCTION

The air-bearing table spacecraft simulator is a test stand, which can be used as a simulation and verification method for the AOCS of satellites. It is composed of a floating platform on which the unit under test is mounted, and a stator that suspends the platform through an air-bearing. The main function of the air-bearing table is to simulate weightlessness and precisely determine the torque response caused by the unit under test, without interfering with the measurement. The air-bearing table must assure that the Center of Gravity (CoG) coincides with the Center of Rotation (CoR). The CoR is given by the spherical shape of the spherical bearing, the CoG by the distribution of mass on the platform. Any distance between these two points will cause unwanted torque to the platform. One feature of the system is therefore to balance by adjusting the CoG prior to measuring.

The principle of the air-bearing table is to use pressurized air to lift a movable system and allow almost frictionless movement in all three rotational axis. The main task of the air-bearing table is to simulate environmental conditions such as weightlessness and force-free rotation of a satellite or single components. An spherical air-bearing consists of a spheroid cap (calotte) which is settled in an equivalently shaped stator at the bottom. When pressurized air is inserted into the gap, the calotte floats, and can freely turn in all three rotational axes. The satellite can then be mounted onto the calotte. In an ideal case, the air-bearing can sustain the platform and allow frictionless rotation, without contributing disturbances torques. When the Center of Gravity (CoG) and Center of Rotation (CoR) are not equivalent, a disturbance torque will be induced. Ideally the unit under test of such a three axis air bearing is balanced in such a way that it is indifferent. The presented paper shows design and model of a spacecraft simulator with three degrees of freedom in rotation without external forces. The main effort is to match the CoG with the CoR. Only when these two points match closely, the system becomes indifferent and

the simulated environment is free of outer forces. An automated system is introduced that can statically eliminate mass imbalances by means of linear actuators.

An air-bearing based 3-DOF simulator for small satellite tests has been designed and build at Berlin Space Technologies GmbH to provide tests for satellites and payloads. The key design parameters and performance of the automated balancing mechanism is presented and discussed in this paper.

SPACECRAFT SIMULATOR DESIGN WITH 3 DOF

The spacecraft simulator is a mechatronic system with the function to provide an environment free of outer torques for the satellite. The spacecraft simulator consists out of several components which shall be introduced shortly. Figure 1 shows a schematic of the basic spacecraft sim-

Figure 1: Mechanical schematic of the spacecraft simulators principle

ulator principle. To support the satellite unit under test (1), an adaption platform (2) is required. The platform provides a rigid structure with an aluminum plate that supports the unit under test and accommodates the on-board measurement setup, actuators and control electronics. This adaption platform is supported by the spherical air bearing (3) on which it floats upon. Compensation masses (4) are connected to the platform. The air-bearing is supported by the stator structure (5). To fixate the platform in reference to the stator, a hold mechanism (6) can be lifted up. This mechanism is integrated into the pedestal and can also support the platform when no pressure is present. The CoR (\odot) of the spherical bearing is given by the bearing's geometry. The upper CoG (\otimes) represents the CoG of the unit under test. The lower illustrated CoG represents the center of the supporting platform. The total center of mass distribution of all floating parts, the satellite platform including the unit under test,

must match to the CoR. For a configuration as in figure 1 it can be seen, that although ideally the satellites CoG should match the CoR a unit under test must be slightly higher to compensate the additional mass of the supporting platform. Such a design is normally stable since only the platform itself lowers the CoG when no unit under test is present. The platform is able to work completely self-sufficient without any additional umbilical connection. For this purpose it is equipped with sensors, actuators, control electronics and power supplies. The complete simulator environment includes a compressor (7) to supply the bearing with air. For interfacing with a user an external computer (8) is connected wireless to the system. A laser diode (9) is connected to the simulator to level the table and calibrate the sensors.

Figure 2: Environment of the spacecraft simulators

SPHERICAL AIR-BEARING DESIGN

In general bearings can be systematically classified by their direction of stress, relative movement and movement pattern. Another classification is based on the used lubricant. The following introduction into gas bearing theory is based on Bartz[1] and Schroter[15]. In general two main types of gas lubricated bearings can be distinguished: aerostatic and aerodynamic. Aerodynamic bearings create the required pressure by relative movement between the bearing's surfaces. These require a high relative velocity between the surfaces. In contrary aerostatic bearings require external pressure to be pushed into the bearing's gap, for instance by nozzles. Even with no velocity between the bearing's surfaces the pressure will ensure a gap lift.

The static parameters describe the long-term behavior, for instance the equilibrium between the static lift force by the pressure and the load force. The uplift force is created by pressure attacking on the two surfaces, here the cap (top) and the calotte (bottom) of the gas bearing. The maximum bearing lift capacity is therefore described by the surface and the pressure distribution. When the gap height is higher, the overall pressure along the surface will lower and the resulting force

will be lower as the gas flow increases, hence the actual bearing lift force depends as well on the gap height. The change of lift force in respective to gap height is described by the bearing stiffness. The maximum uplift force attacks when the gap size is zero $h = 0$. The idealized uplift force caused by a supply pressure p_0 can be calculated with the bearings surface A . For a flat disk this is done in eq. (1), with r_a disk outer diameter, p_a environmental pressure and p_0 the bearing's supply pressure.

$$F_{h=0} = C_c \cdot A \cdot (p_0 - p_a) = C_c \cdot r_a^2 \cdot \pi \cdot (p_0 - p_a), \quad (1)$$

$$0 \leq C_c \leq 1. \quad (2)$$

This extends the original equation [1] by a dimensionless performance coefficient C_c . A value of $C_c = 1$ states ideal pressure distribution over the complete surface of the bearing. As shown in figure ?? the pressure is usually not evenly distributed. The key static parameters for single and multiple nozzle bearings are the bearing surface and the pressure distribution. The pressure distribution can be influenced by (1) pocket size / hole diameter, (2) venting grooves. Usually the performance for bearings with a discrete amount of nozzles/pockets is found to be $C_c \approx 0.2 - 0.5$, depending on the amount, design and the distribution of nozzles. For distributed micro-nozzles $C_c \approx 1$ is assumed [1].

MODEL AND CONTROL OF THE FLOATING PLATFORM

The platform is the moving part of the spacecraft simulator that floats upon the bearing. The model is similar to a physical pendulum, where the pendulum length is equal to the length of the vector \vec{r} pointing from the CoR to the CoG.

The rigid-body model of the platform with unit under test has the combined parameters mass $m = m_{(p+s)}$, principal moment of inertia tensor $\underline{I} = (I_1, I_2, I_3)^T$ and initial displacement \vec{r} . The vector \vec{r} points from the CoR to CoG. The platform movement is described by the angular velocity ω and angular acceleration $\dot{\omega}$.

1

The body torque τ_{euler} follows from the Euler equation rigid body dynamics (4) with the angular velocity vector $\underline{\omega}$ around the body principal axes and angular momentum of the payload L . The torque τ_{grav} , exerted by the mis-

¹Reference frames: Throughout this thesis different orientation frames will be used: the reference frame (R), the body frame (B) and the Local Vertical/ Local Horizontal (LVLH) frame (L). The reference frame is an arbitrarily chosen initial frame, whereas the body frame is fixed to the body's principal axes. The LVLH frame is used to describe the ground reference frame, where the x-y plane in a LVLH is equal to the Local Tangent Plane. Here the LVLH is not fixed by conventions using cardinal directions.

Figure 3: Schematics of spacecraft simulator with displacement masses with Center of Rotation (\odot), Center of Gravity (\otimes) and the initial mass displacement vector \vec{r}_0 .

alignment between the gravity vector and the mass displacement vector, is described in eq. (5).

$$\sum \tau = 0. \quad (3)$$

$$\tau_{euler} = \dot{L} + ({}^B \underline{\omega} \times L) = \begin{pmatrix} I_1 \dot{\omega}_1 \\ I_2 \dot{\omega}_2 \\ I_3 \dot{\omega}_3 \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} (I_3 - I_2) \omega_2 \omega_3 \\ (I_1 - I_3) \omega_3 \omega_1 \\ (I_2 - I_1) \omega_1 \omega_2 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (4)$$

$$\tau_{grav} = -m \cdot (\vec{g} \times \vec{r}). \quad (5)$$

... with the complete spacecraft simulator platform rigid-body then described by ...

$$\underline{I} \cdot \dot{\underline{\omega}} + (\underline{\omega} \times \underline{I} \cdot \underline{\omega}) = m \cdot (\vec{g} \times \vec{r}) - \tau_{ext}. \quad (6)$$

In this equation \underline{I} are the principal moments of inertia and m the mass of the platform including the unit under test, the platform angular velocity $\underline{\omega}$ and the gravity vector \vec{g} . The mass displacement vector can be split into an unknown initial vector \vec{r}_0 , and the vector $\delta\vec{r}$ caused by the displacement of compensation masses.

$$\vec{r} = \vec{r}_0 + \delta\vec{r}. \quad (7)$$

$$\vec{r} = \frac{1}{m_\Sigma} \sum_{i=0}^n m_i \mathbf{r}_i = \frac{1}{m_\Sigma} \left(m_0 \vec{r}_0 + \sum_{i=1}^n m_{c,i} \cdot \vec{r}_{c,i} \right). \quad (8)$$

$$\vec{r}_{b,i} = d_{c,i} \cdot \vec{u}_{c,i}. \quad (9)$$

The constant moment of mass $m_0 \cdot \vec{r}_0$, caused by the platform and unit under test, including the compensation masses at their initial position \vec{p}_i . The dynamic moment of mass caused by one compensation mass is described by $m_{c,i} \cdot \vec{r}_{c,i}$. The displacement vector of each balancing mass can be described by its initial location vector $\vec{p}_{c,i}$, and an offset $d_{c,i}$ along its movement direction vector $\vec{u}_{c,i}$. The dynamic moment of mass caused by the i th compensation mass can be expressed by the displacement

\vec{d}_i and mass $m_{c,i}$.

$$\delta\vec{r} = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^n m_i \vec{u}_i \delta\vec{d}_i = \frac{1}{m} \mathbf{G} \delta\vec{d}. \quad (10)$$

$$\mathbf{G} = [m_1 u_1, m_2 u_2, m_3 u_3]. \quad (11)$$

This model has some nonlinear correlations: First, the Euler equation of rigid body dynamics is a nonlinear coupling between the three axes. Second, the gravity induced torque is a nonlinear function $f(\vec{r}, \vec{g})$ of mass displacement and gravity vector.

An initial mass displacement \vec{r}_0 can be cancelled out by moving compensation masses m_i . A two stage mass compensation consisting of major ($m \approx 1 \text{ kg}$) that can be adjusted manually and minor ($m \approx 0.12 \text{ kg}$) on precise linear tables is implemented. The linear tables can be driven by a stepper motor and allow a displacement resolution better than $1 \mu\text{m}$. The given design allows a theoretical reduction of gravity induced torque down to $3.67 \times 10^{-7} \text{ Nm}$.

COMPARISON OF AUTOMATED MASS BALANCING METHODS

Several strategies will be introduced to compensate the displacement and balance the spacecraft simulator platform. A key challenge for the direct compensation method is determining the CoG, as it cannot be directly estimated from torque. This section shall introduce concepts of mass balancing, as the spacecraft simulator has to be balanced before measurements can take place, by compensating the initial mass displacement. The CoG is shifted by balancing compensation masses in all three axes. To perform mass balancing a method often proposed is estimation and iterative compensation based on external torque [9]. Other approaches rely on constant counter-torque created by reaction wheels to determine the CoG [12]. To support mass balancing two different control law types are examined in detail: The **direct** approach compensates the displacement directly based on estimations. A consecutive approach to first vertically and then horizontally is proposed. The **adaptive** approach first minimizes the torque and adaptively compensates the displacement. The key difference is the required hardware: the torque driven approach can be realized with fewer actuators. A disadvantage is the lack of torque control possibilities during most of the balancing process. Table 1 lists the different requirements for the compensation strategies. Reduction of actuators is favorable, since the additional mass and inertia introduced can distort actual spacecraft simulation. A comprehensive approach is the "automatic adaptive mass balancing control" as adapted by Kim and Agrawal [11]. Using additional torque exchange devices to first stabilize the system with a closed-loop feedback control law, and then adaptively adjust the masses using a second adaptive control law. The adaption rule compensates the mass displacement with three linear actuators gradually. The

	Linear tables	Reaction Wheels
Direct	✓	
Adaptive	✓	✓

Table 1: Overview of required actuator hardware for automated mass balancing strategies

adaptive approach allows for robust control design, but requires additional hardware to be included on the payload platform. An advantage is the possibility of direct torque compensation. As seen in [11], manual adjustment possibly yields a higher precision than adaptive control. In addition, the higher amount of actuators causes additional inertia and mass that negatively influences actual tests.

To automate the balancing procedure a proportional controller is invoked to cancel out the initial mass displacement. A direct compensation law is chosen, such as:

$$\delta\dot{\vec{r}} = -\underline{K}(\vec{r}_0 + \delta\vec{r}) \quad (12)$$

The vector $\delta\vec{r}$ is the new mass displacement caused by moving the compensation masses. The vector mass displacement vector $\vec{r} = \vec{r}_0 + \delta\vec{r}$ can not be directly determined by measurement of torque and gravity vector. Instead a vertical displacement estimate is first used for horizontal balancing. After the horizontal displacement has been cancelled out, vertical displacement is performed.

Direct compensation of mass imbalance

The equation of motion (4) can be formulated using the Vector Cross Product Matrix (13), which can express a cross product by means of a matrix algebra (14).

$$[\mathbf{a}]_{\times} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -a_3 & a_2 \\ a_3 & 0 & -a_1 \\ -a_2 & a_1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (13)$$

$$\underline{\dot{L}} + [\omega]_{\times} \underline{L} = m [g]_{\times} (\vec{r}_0 + \delta\vec{r}) \quad (14)$$

Let the control law be therefore be a proportional controller to decrease the displacement, with \underline{K} a positive-definitive diagonal matrix.

$$\delta\dot{\vec{r}} = -\underline{K}(\vec{r}_0 + \delta\vec{r}), \quad (15)$$

... with the Lyapunov candidate function: ...

$$V(\vec{r} + \delta\vec{r}) = \frac{1}{2} (\vec{r}_0 + \delta\vec{r})^T (\vec{r}_0 + \delta\vec{r}), \quad (16)$$

... and the Lyapunov candidate derivative ...

$$\dot{V}(\vec{r}_0 + \delta\vec{r}) = (\vec{r}_0 + \delta\vec{r})^T \cdot \delta\dot{\vec{r}} \quad (17)$$

$$= -(\vec{r}_0 + \delta\vec{r})^T \cdot \underline{K} \cdot (\vec{r}_0 + \delta\vec{r}). \quad (18)$$

The derivative of the Lyapunov function is strictly negative, hence the control law is Lyapunov stable and the displacement ($\vec{r}_0 + \delta\vec{r}$) is converging to zero. With the transformation into the actual compensation mass movement using the Matrix \underline{G} (11), the actuation law can be stated as in eq. 19.

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{\delta\vec{d}} &= \underline{G}^{-1} \cdot m \cdot \dot{\delta\vec{r}} \\ &= -\underline{G}^{-1} \cdot m \cdot \underline{K} \cdot (\vec{r}_0 + \delta\vec{r}).\end{aligned}\quad (19)$$

TEST RESULTS

Figure 4: The air-bearing test stand including a adaption platform mass dummy with adaption platform and backup lock mechanism (right).

The automatic horizontal balancing control started in a tilted initial attitude and was able to cancel out the displacement and eliminate the oscillation induced by underestimating the vertical displacement. The results of one balancing procedure is shown in figures 5 to 8.² Vertical balancing canceled out an initial pre-existing vertical displacement. Due to the uneven disturbance torques caused by the payload in the two axes, the balancing caused instability in the less stable axis.

It can be observed that at a good equilibrium the air-bearing platform becomes susceptible to environmental air flow, such as caused by ventilation or passing persons, can cause a disturbance torque. This can only be avoided in a calm, unmoved environment. Any unbalance in the surface of the bearing can possible cause a disturbance torque based on the actual wetting of the surface.

²Rotation formalism: The **Tait-Bryan** e.g. Euler angles are described by three consecutive rotations, one about each axis. For air and space vehicles, the order in which the rotations occur is by convention (z-y'-x'') which will be used further on, according to DIN 9300 / ISO 1151 [4]. **Orientation angles** φ describe instantaneous rotations around each axis. These describe the angle between the plane XY and the respective axes X and Y and are independent angles.

SUMMARY

In the scope of this paper an air-bearing based spacecraft simulator has been developed, constructed and verified. The spacecraft simulator platform has been optimized to comply with the requirement to carry and balance a specific satellite. An adaption platform has been built to mount smaller and lighter test units and simulate a unit under test. A mechanism to limit the platform's tilt and lift it above the bearing has been implemented and proven working. In simulations it has been shown that compensation of initial mass balances can be performed directly by consecutive balancing first horizontally and then vertically. The complete spacecraft simulator was built and assembled. First tests have shown that the platform is able to carry the unit under test and cancel out a displacement of the Center of Gravity. The occurring disturbance torques did not allow for compensation of gravity torque better than $1 \times 10^{-3} Nm$, in one axis reduction of disturbance torque to below $1 \times 10^{-3} Nm$ could be performed. The requirement to reduce torque is therefore non-conformant with a margin of more than two orders of magnitude. The precision of gravitational disturbances adjustment was limited due to additional disturbance torques. A lack of stiffness of the payload dummy used for testing has been identified as one of the sources of disturbance torque.

A measurement that can capture the attitude, the motion and the torque of the simulator platform has been designed and implemented. The determination of torque does not provide the resolution required for evaluating the disturbance torques of very low magnitude for the complete operating range due to derived sensor noise. Despite that, the compensation precision of the CoG is not negatively influenced by the torque precision, and can therefore still be performed with very good precision due to the low-pass behavior of the platform plant.

- Design, setup and evaluation of an air-bearing based spacecraft simulator for testing of satellites up to 100 kg with a tilt freedom of 14.7°.
 - Mass balancing of the floating platform to achieve a gravity induced torque of less than $8 \times 10^{-3} Nm$.
 - Automated direct mass balancing control for vertical and horizontal balancing.
 - Indirect determination of torque with a accuracy between $7.76 \times 10^{-3} Nm$ (3σ) to $1.7 \times 10^{-4} Nm$ (3σ), depending on inertia estimate quality and filter time.
 - Automated locking/unlocking of the platform to avoid damage to the air-bearing.
- ⇒ The requirement of $1 \times 10^{-5} Nm$ to reduce gravitational disturbances with the dummy payload and torque determination are non-conformant by more than two orders of magnitude.

Figure 5: Test case Table4: Orientation angles during automatic balancing.

Figure 6: Test case Table4: Torque.

Figure 7: Test case Table4: Stepper motor positions, aligned towards final position.

Figure 8: Test case Table4: Angular velocity.

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